

ON THE ISSUE OF FORMING OF INNOVATIVE INFORMATION AND MANAGEMENT ENVIRONMENT OF THE SECONDARY GENERAL EDUCATIONAL SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The research is devoted to the actual problem of the formation of an innovative information and management environment of a secondary school, caused by the demands of the digitalization of education. The innovative information and management environment incorporates the features of an optimal management environment and an innovative environment, namely, information conditions for the effective organization of management activities of a director of a secondary school based on innovative technologies. As innovative technologies, the research uses modern ICT, in particular cloud and network technologies.

Keywords: information and educational environment, innovative information and management environment, informatization of education, information and communication technologies.

Introduction

Today we live in a world where digitalization acts as a factor in global social development. The key task of education is the training of personnel that meets the needs of society. The factor of digitalization of the educational environment lies in the massive development of information technologies, expressed in the speed and availability of high-speed Internet.

New technologies are emerging on the world market that require educational organizations to use management technologies that allow them to manage innovation. Educational organizations, and in particular general education schools, must learn not only to predict changes, but also to introduce innovations in such a way as to gain a competitive advantage for themselves. Educational organizations must become open to the changing world, they must be competitive, constantly improve the quality of their services. The school must strive to meet the rapidly changing interests of consumers, they must quickly respond to the changes taking place in the modern world.

The research is devoted to the actual problem of the formation of an innovative information and management environment of a secondary school as an element of the electronic educational environment caused by the demands of the digitalization of education.

The modern school is an open social and pedagogical system, which includes the interaction of pedagogical, student and parent teams as equal partners who strive for dialogue, interpersonal communication, broad social partnership, the purpose of which is to improve the quality of education as a process and the quality of education as its result [2].

What does the term "digital school" include? The term "digital school" means a general education institution that is equipped with modern digital equipment, software and effectively uses it in the management and educational process, taking into account its own characteristics (financial situation, readiness of teachers and managerial staff). An innovative information and management environment should contribute to the formation not only of the head and the teaching staff, but also of the students of the qualities and skills of the 21st century, namely, media literacy, the ability to continue

education, the willingness to work in a team, creativity, communication and professional mobility.

It is necessary to systematically develop an innovative information and management environment of an educational organization based on the introduction of modern digital technologies into the managerial, methodological and pedagogical process.

Literature review

The effectiveness of the managerial activity of the director of a secondary general education school directly depends on the conditions of the environment in which he works. At the same time, as Smirnov M.A. described, each person creates his own information environment.

The term "environment" is used to refer to the external conditions relative to a particular person. The term "information environment" is used to refer to the information conditions of human existence. The information environment consists of information resources and infrastructure. At the same time, the information environment represents the necessary conditions for human development. But the degree of its influence on the development of a person depends on the internal characteristics of the person himself, i.e. information needs, information knowledge, skills and competencies.

Andreev A.A. sees this environment as a single information space that combines information, both on traditional and electronic media; computer-telecommunication educational and methodical complexes and technologies of interaction; pedagogical system of a new level, which includes logistical, financial, economic, regulatory and legal support [1].

Ilchenko O. A. positions IEE as a systematically organized set of information, technical, educational and methodological support, which is inextricably linked with a person as a subject of education [5].

According to Tipushkov S. V. an innovative educational space is a motivating information and educational environment within which the system is implemented management of educational, methodological support, a resource base is provided, conditions are cre-

ated for the implementation of professional self-improvement and personal growth of teachers and students [6].

In the course of researching the literature on the research problem, we determined that the information environment consists of information resources and infrastructure. At the same time, the information environment represents the necessary conditions for human development. But the degree of its influence on the development of a person depends on the internal characteristics of the person himself, i.e. information needs, information knowledge, skills and competencies.

It is known that every organization operates in a certain environment. The management environment is the environment in which the management functions. Moreover, each organization usually consists of departments with their own functions and components. They influence the behavior of members of the entire team, especially leaders.

The management environment is divided into the following categories:

- 1) an inert management environment, it lacks interrelated goals of units;
- 2) an aggressive environment that has mutually exclusive goals.
- 3) the optimal environment, which is characterized by the consistency of actions in achieving complementary goals and directs to development based on the creation of optimal and favorable conditions for the functioning of the organization.

Based on the above, we will define the terms "information management environment" and "innovative information management environment".

The information and management environment in our research is used to designate the information conditions for organizing the managerial activities of the director of a secondary school.

The innovative information and management environment incorporates the features of an optimal management environment and an innovative environment, namely, information conditions for the effective organization of management activities of a director of a secondary school based on innovative technologies. As innovative technologies, our research uses modern ICT, in particular cloud and network technologies.

To form an innovative information and management environment of the school, the director must have not only managerial competencies, but also information competencies. In the research [3] under the creative information and communication competency of the principal of general education school is the integration of the principal of the school for the creative use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) into the professional and managerial activities. Only on the basis of their combination is it possible to form an effective information and management environment and improve it to the level of an innovative information and management environment [4].

Discussion

It is known that the management of the school is carried out on the basis of a combination of the principles of self-government of the team and unity of command.

The first level - the director - the main administrative person, on the basis of unity of command, is personally responsible for everything that is done at the school. At the same level there are bodies of collegiate and public administration: the school council, the pedagogical council, self-government bodies. They ensure the unity of the control system as a whole.

The second level of management in the school is the deputy directors. They exercise indirect control. Their main function is to coordinate the activities of all participants in the process in accordance with the goals, plan and expected results.

The third level of school management is carried out by methodological associations.

The fourth level of school management is carried out at the level of students, parents and teachers on the basis of self-government and the principle of democratization.

Throughout the history of the development of secondary schools, functional responsibilities have been developed for managers at each level of management, which ensures clarity and coherence in school management.

However, in the modern conditions of the information society, when there is a purposeful process of digitalization of education, only a clear distribution of administrative duties based on the managerial competencies of the director and his individual characteristics is not enough. At present, it becomes relevant to ensure the optimality of management processes based on the organization of joint planning, the organization of joint control over the execution of orders, continuous monitoring of their effectiveness based on the timely exchange of information. This can be done on the basis of modern ICT.

In view of the fact that the use of cloud technologies is not associated with additional technical equipment of the subjects of the management process, we proposed a model for organizing school management based on cloud services.

We propose to build an innovative information and management environment for a secondary school, i.e. an artificially built information system that ensures the integration and continuity of all "vertical" and "horizontal" communications in management processes based on the use of cloud technologies such as adaptability, efficiency and virtualization.

Adaptability implies the possibility of adapting the innovative information and management environment to the existing technical equipment of the school. Efficiency allows to carry out all organizational management processes in real time through the use of virtual services. Virtualization implies the creation of a virtual information system for storing various school management data. Table 1 highlights cloud services in the context of management processes.

Table 1.

Functions of cloud services in an innovative information management environment (on the example of Google+)

Functions of cloud services (on the example of Google+)	Service
Collection and storage of data	Google Disk
Creation of joint documents, plans, reports	Google Drive
Discussion of plans and reports	Google Meet Google Blog, gmail, GoogleTalk, GoogleVoice,
Activity planning	GoogleCalendar
Establishing feedback with subjects of management	GoogleForm

We define the necessary components for the formation of an innovative information and management environment:

1. Technical components: computer (or tablet, mobile phone, netbook, laptop), communication lines for accessing the Internet,
2. Software components: browser, cloud services (there are Internet networks),
3. Services: a company that provides cloud computing services,
4. Skills: information skills; Internet skills, skills in working with office applications; skills in working with web applications, skills in working with cloud services, skills in working with social networks.

The following system elements will function in the innovative information and management environment:

- 1-level:
 - virtual director,
 - virtual tips by category,
- 2-level:
 - virtual deputies,
- 3-level:
 - virtual communities,
 - virtual methodical associations,
- 4-level:
 - virtual teachers' rooms,
 - virtual classrooms,
 - virtual parents,
 - virtual documents (school management data).

Fig.1. Scheme of organization of the innovative information and management environment of the school

The formation of an innovative information and management environment is carried out on the basis of several stages: preparatory, formative and developing.

The preparatory stage includes:

- 1) improving the information skills of the director on the basis of continuous professional development, either by self-education or at advanced training courses;

- 2) improving the information and communication skills of the entire school staff through the organization of thematic seminars on the use of cloud technologies;

- 3) creation of personal virtual offices for each subject of the management process.

Virtual offices are created on the basis of cloud services. They are designed to store data and to organize vertical and horizontal communications. Virtual offices allow you to:

- fast data collection,
- access to data anywhere and anytime,
- to carry out system storage of data of large volumes,
- storage of all data in one place,
- speed up data transfer speed,
- accelerate the speed of awareness of the student and his parents,
- organize team work on documents,
- ensure the availability of documents for each member of the team,
- ensure the transparency of the activities of each participant,
- organization of joint monitoring over the fulfillment of the goal and objectives.

After the preparatory stage, the formative stage begins, which includes the collection and formation of data in electronic form and uploading them to virtual cabinets. At the initial stage, it is recommended to create a virtual environment of only the 1st and 2nd levels. Having mastered the principles of functioning of the innovative information and communication environment on the example of the first two levels, you can proceed to the creation of other levels of virtualization of the school's management environment.

Conclusion

The proposed model for organizing management activities in a school, developed on the basis of using the capabilities of cloud technologies, improves the management efficiency of a director of a secondary general education school due to:

- 1) optimization of information processes in management;

- 2) through the use of the functions of informatization processes in management;

- 3) by increasing motivation for modern ICT.

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